

Assessing institutional readiness for language- aware assessments

A FOCUS GROUP REPORT

TASK FORCE 3 – POLICY ADVICE AND IMPLEMENTATION

MULTILINGUALISM AND LANGUAGE BIASES IN RESEARCH ASSESSMENT WORKING GROUP

Table of Contents

List of Figures.....	1
List of Acronyms.....	3
Acknowledgements.....	3
Key points of the report.....	4
1. Introduction.....	5
2. Building the questionnaire as a self-assessment tool.....	6
3. Composition of the Focus Group.....	9
4. Responses as performance of self-assessment.....	11
5. Recommendations for the future use of the TF3 questionnaire.....	22
Organisations affiliated to this WG.....	24
CoARA.....	26
Working Group Overview.....	26

List of Figures

Figure 1: Timeline of organisations' efforts to support multilingualism policies and combat language bias in research assessment (n=8)	11
Figure 2: Existence of a language policy that considers research(er) assessment (n=8).....	11
Figure 3: Integration of language policy in internal assessment processes (n=8).....	12
Figure 4: Organisation's recognition and valuation of outputs irrespective of language (n=8)	13
Figure 5: Challenges and difficulties faced by organisation members in adopting multilingualism practices (n=8)	13
Figure 6: Involvement of researchers across disciplines and career stages in developing procedures that recognise research diversity, including language perspectives (n=8).....	14
Figure 7: Organisation's support for publication databases that consider local languages (n=8).....	15
Figure 8: Consideration of publications in all languages when using metrics-based evaluation systems (n=8).....	16
Figure 9: Organisation's adherence to DORA recommendations for valuing high-quality research regardless of publishing language or channel (n=8).....	17
Figure 10: Organisation's adherence to the principle that writing in English does not confer superior merit (n=8)	17
Figure 11: Organisation's consideration of language and potential language biases in planning evaluation, assessment, or funding procedures (n=8)	18
Figure 12: Organisation's recognition that multilingualism favours socially relevant research and contributes to sustaining cultural diversity (n=8).....	19
Figure 13: Organisation's consideration of excellence in local research and value of local, regional, and national languages (n=8).....	20
Figure 14: Organisation's endorsement of international declarations beyond CoARA, including Helsinki, DORA, and others (n=8).....	21

Document Information	
Output Title	Assessing institutional readiness for language-aware assessments: a focus group report
Working Group	Multilingualism and Language Biases in Research Assessment
Topic	Policy Advice and Implementation
Draft Version	1.0
Publication Date	Pending
Output Type	Publication/ Report
Producer(s)	Task Force 3
Project Leader(s)	Martine Garnier-Rizet, Emanuelle Gardan, Monica Dietl
Editor(s)	Fotis Mystakopoulos (https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9354-3754)
Reviewer(s)	Petteri Laihonen, Susanna Fiorini, Martine Garnier-Rizet, Janne Pölönen
Other contributors	Task Force 3
Status	Final

Please cite as:

Multilingualism and Language Biases in Research Assessment Working Group, Task Force 3 – Policy Advice and Implementation. (2025). Assessing institutional readiness for language-aware assessments: A focus group report. CoARA WG on Multilingualism and Language Biases in Research Assessment. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17915543>

Revision history			
Version	Date	Revised by	Comments
0.1	10.11.2025	Fotis Mystakopoulos	First Draft
0.2	10.12.2025	Petteri Laihonen, Susanna Fiorini, Martine Garnier-Rizet	Revision and Proofreading
0.5	30.12.2025	Fotis Mystakopoulos	Adding the content in the CoARA Template and finalising copyediting
1.0	12.6.2026	Fotis Mystakopoulos, Janne Pölönen	Publication Ready

List of Acronyms

CoARA	Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment
CRIS	Working Group
DORA	Declaration on Research Assessment
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FECYT	Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (Fundación Española para la Ciencia y la Tecnología)
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
REF	Research Excellence Framework (UK)
TF3	Task Force 3
WG	Working Group

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the members of the Focus Group who generously contributed their time and expertise to this study. In particular, we gratefully acknowledge the following individuals and their organisations for their participation and for consenting to be named: Pilar Rico Castro (Fundación Española para la Ciencia y la Tecnología), Ozen Nergis Seckin Dolcerocca (University of Bologna), Constance Burgod (Institut National du Cancer), and Paul Spence (King's College London, Department of Digital Humanities). Their insights and institutional perspectives were instrumental in shaping the findings and recommendations presented in this report.

Key points of the report:

- **Dual function of the questionnaire**

The TF3 questionnaire serves both as a self-assessment instrument, helping institutions to reflect on their internal practices, and as a capacity-evaluation tool that reveals the organisational, technical, and cultural readiness needed to advance multilingual fairness in research assessment.

- **Holistic view of multilingual readiness**

By combining questions on policy, governance, practice, infrastructure, evaluation, and values, the questionnaire provides a 360-degree perspective on how institutions translate commitments to multilingualism into actionable mechanisms.

- **Mapping maturity across contexts**

Responses expose a spectrum of institutional maturity, ranging from systems where multilingualism is structurally embedded in law or governance, to contexts where it remains aspirational or departmental. This variation demonstrates the usefulness of the instrument for benchmarking progress across diverse institutional and national settings.

- **Self-reflection and organisational learning**

The act of responding to the questionnaire prompts internal reflection: institutions identify not only their strengths but also latent inconsistencies between declared values and operational realities. This reflective process supports iterative improvement and fosters shared learning among participants.

- **Evidence for policy coherence and reform pathways**

When analysed collectively, the responses offer an emerging evidence base for aligning multilingualism with broader reform frameworks such as CoARA and DORA. They also provide actionable insights into where institutional capacity, policy, infrastructure, or evaluator competence, must be strengthened to ensure fair and inclusive assessment practices.

1. Introduction

Task Force 3 (TF3) of the CoARA Working Group on Multilingualism and Language Biases in Research Assessment focuses on developing actionable solutions to address the unequal treatment of languages in research evaluation. Its work aims to transform high-level commitments to multilingualism into practical policies and procedures that institutions can adopt and implement.

To support this mandate, TF3 initiated a Focus Group to collect practical, bottom-up insights from organisations committed to reform. As part of this process, the aim was to invite national research funding organisations, research performing organisations, universities, and scientific associations to participate on the basis of their role in implementing research assessment processes. Participants were asked to share challenges, assess the feasibility of emerging recommendations, and propose solutions and procedural innovations that could support linguistic diversity.

The benefit of this exercise is that rather than examining multilingualism through quantitative indicators or document analysis alone, this work adopts a qualitative approach that engages directly with organisational actors responsible for assessment implementation. Through their responses, the Focus Group provides contextualised insights into institutional practices, decision-making constraints, and perceptions of feasibility that are not readily visible in policy documents or bibliometric data. This perspective is essential for understanding how commitments to linguistic diversity are interpreted and operationalised within complex organisational environments, and for identifying the specific challenges and opportunities that shape assessment reform in practice.

This work is based on an “ideal scenario” framework, envisioning a research environment where scholars can publish and communicate freely in their language of choice. In this scenario, evaluation focuses on the quality and fairness of research outputs rather than on language hierarchies. Using a Focus Group methodology, the study examines the institutional factors that either enable or hinder such a scenario. It identifies both barriers and facilitating conditions across different contexts. Rather than proposing fixed solutions, the intervention uses participants’ feedback as a tool for institutional self-assessment, providing a starting point for organisations seeking to address language bias in their evaluation systems.

The analysis focuses on three main components. First, it outlines the development of the TF3 questionnaire, conceived as both a self-assessment instrument for institutions and a tool for evaluating language competencies in research. Second, it presents the rationale and design of the Focus Groups, which synthesise participants’ experiences to map current practices and identify conditions necessary for reducing language bias. Finally, it offers preliminary conclusions and recommendations for future research, particularly regarding strategies for implementing and refining the questionnaire.

2. Building the questionnaire as a self-assessment tool.

Policy and governance

The first cluster of questions explores whether institutions have developed explicit frameworks for addressing multilingualism and language bias within research assessment. These questions examine both the existence of formal policies and their temporal development, reflecting institutional maturity in this area. Institutions are asked to indicate when their efforts to support multilingualism and counter language bias began, distinguishing between actions initiated before or after signing the CoARA Agreement. This timeline helps to situate language-related reforms within broader institutional change processes. Further questions address whether organisations have a formal language policy that extends to researcher assessment, and whether such policies are concretely integrated into internal evaluation procedures. The goal here is to distinguish symbolic commitments from operational realities, identifying cases where multilingualism is embedded in organisational governance rather than existing only as an aspirational statement.

Key dimensions captured:

- Policy existence and timeline (Q1–Q3)
- Integration of language considerations into assessment governance
- Degree of institutional maturity and commitment

Practices and institutional culture

The second cluster examines how institutional cultures and practices enable or hinder the recognition of multilingual outputs. It invites organisations to reflect on whether their assessment procedures value contributions irrespective of language and whether multilingualism is seen as integral to the social and cultural relevance of research. Institutions are also asked whether staff and researchers face challenges in adopting multilingual practices, which helps identify structural barriers such as resource limitations, evaluation disincentives, or lack of translation support. A key component concerns inclusivity in decision-making: whether researchers from different disciplines and career stages are involved in shaping the policies and mechanisms that recognise linguistic and epistemic diversity. This participation is a marker of a living, community-based policy process rather than a top-down directive.

Key dimensions captured:

- Recognition of multilingual outputs (Q4)
- Barriers and challenges experienced by researchers (Q5)
- Inclusive participation in developing assessment frameworks (Q6)
- Institutional culture and collective ownership of reform

Technical and infrastructural capacities

This section focuses on the infrastructural layer, the digital and data systems that underpin research assessment. The questionnaire asks whether institutions support publication databases or repositories that account for local-language outputs, and whether these systems are interoperable with international infrastructures such as OpenAlex or OpenAIRE. This focus reflects an understanding that fair multilingual representation is not possible without technical capacity to register and track non-English research outputs. Similarly, institutions are asked whether their metrics-based systems are configured to include publications in all languages, a critical factor in avoiding data-driven forms of bias.

Key dimensions captured:

- Use of inclusive research information systems (Q7)
- Metrics and database configurations for multilingual data (Q8)
- Infrastructural readiness and FAIR alignment

Evaluation and assessment practices

A central group of questions examines how institutions operationalise fairness in evaluation. These include whether expert-based assessments follow DORA-aligned principles, valuing quality over language or journal prestige, and whether institutions formally endorse the idea that English-language publication does not inherently confer greater merit. This section also explores the practical competence of evaluators, assessing whether they possess the necessary language skills to review outputs in multiple languages. Such capacities are essential to ensure that the formal recognition of multilingualism is matched by the ability to apply it fairly in practice. Finally, the questionnaire asks whether institutions consider language and language bias already at the planning stage of evaluation or funding procedures, an indicator of proactive rather than reactive policy design.

Key dimensions captured:

- DORA-aligned evaluation practices (Q9)
- Rejection of English-language bias (Q10)
- Evaluator language competence (Q13)
- Early integration of language fairness into assessment planning (Q15)

Values and equity of multilingualism

Beyond technical and procedural matters, several questions capture the normative orientation of institutions, their understanding of why multilingualism matters. Institutions are invited to indicate whether they believe that multilingualism enhances social relevance, sustains cultural diversity, and strengthens local research excellence. These questions move the reflection beyond compliance and toward values-based reform. They invite organisations to consider whether their assessment

frameworks are aligned with the principles of equity, diversity, and the collective benefit of knowledge, which are core tenets of both Open Science and CoARA.

Key dimensions captured:

- Recognition of multilingualism as a social and cultural value (Q11–Q12)
- Alignment with public-good and inclusivity principles

Alignment with broader reform movements

The final section situates institutional efforts within the wider landscape of global reform initiatives. Institutions are asked whether they have endorsed complementary frameworks such as DORA, the Helsinki Initiative, or other international declarations that address assessment reform and multilingualism, beyond the CoARA Commitments. This helps to map the coherence of institutional commitments across multiple policy levels. An open-ended question invites participants to provide additional insights, enabling qualitative reflection on context-specific challenges, innovative practices, or policy needs that may not fit predefined categories.

Key dimensions captured:

- Global alignment and cross-initiative participation (Q14)
- Reflexive self-assessment and qualitative input (Q16)

Summary

Overall, the questionnaire acts as both a mirror and a map. It allows institutions to measure their current standing regarding multilingualism in research assessment while identifying areas requiring capacity-building or policy alignment. It also functions as a competence evaluation tool, assessing whether institutions possess the necessary frameworks, infrastructures, and human capacities to ensure equitable assessment across languages. In essence, the TF3 questionnaire operationalises two core objectives:

- To support institutional self-assessment and reflection on language fairness in research evaluation.
- To identify and strengthen language competencies across systems, from policy design and evaluator training to metrics and infrastructure.

3. Composition of the Focus Group

This section analyses the rationale for participant recruitment, the degree to which the selection criteria were fulfilled, and the representativeness of the participants engaged in the TF3 Focus Group on multilingualism in research assessment. The analysis is based on the information available from the collected responses. The rationale for participant selection aligns closely with the overarching CoARA commitment to address multilingualism and mitigate language bias in research assessment. Since TF3 focuses on Policy Advice and Implementation, the recruitment strategy was designed to capture practical, bottom-up perspectives from organisations actively engaged in assessment processes. The Focus Group was therefore expected to test the feasibility of TF3's emerging ideas and recommendations, identify institutional barriers to supporting multilingualism, and contribute concrete, implementation-oriented feedback that could inform future guidance and policy development. Participants were sought primarily within the CoARA community, ideally individuals directly involved in implementing or advising on assessment reform within their institutions.

Based on the responses received, the selection criteria appear to have been broadly met. The participant group includes a mix of research funding and performing organisations, universities, and national or international research bodies. The final sample combines national research councils and scientific institutes, such as the Research Council of Finland, the French National Cancer Institute, and FECYT, with higher education institutions including Queen Mary University of London, King's College London, the Universities of Warwick and Reading, and the University of Bologna. Several respondents explicitly referenced their institution's endorsement of CoARA or related initiatives such as DORA, confirming a shared commitment to responsible and equitable assessment reform. Collectively, these organisations represent entities directly involved in designing, implementing, or evaluating research assessment procedures, thus providing the Focus Group with informed and practice-based input.

The composition of the group demonstrates diversity in linguistic and national contexts, which is a key strength of the sample. It encompasses institutions operating in predominantly English-language systems (for example, UK universities), in bilingual or trilingual environments where national legislation defines language use (such as Finland), and in countries where local languages maintain a strong role in scholarly communication (such as Spain and Italy). The institutions also differ in their stage of engagement with multilingualism: some have established, long-term practices, while others are only recently developing policies linked to their CoARA commitments. This variation enhances the group's ability to assess whether the questionnaire can be effectively applied across diverse cultural and institutional contexts.

However, some limitations in representativeness should be acknowledged. Notably, participation from national, European, or international scientific associations was limited, even though these organisations were part of the intended target group. Such associations could have provided valuable disciplinary perspectives and insights into the experiences of individual researchers, particularly across

different career stages, which may not be fully captured when participation is concentrated among institutional actors.

In summary, the Focus Group achieved a balanced and diverse sample of institutions that are both committed to reform and positioned to influence or implement changes in research assessment. The geographical and linguistic breadth of the participants, together with their varied levels of policy maturity, offers TF3 a robust foundation for identifying feasibility issues, mapping existing gaps, and co-developing practical pathways for integrating multilingualism into research assessment systems.

4. Responses as performance of self-assessment

Policy and governance

When assessing policy readiness and integration, the responses reveal a continuum of institutional maturity in addressing multilingualism within research assessment. Collectively, the findings allow organisations to situate themselves in relation to both the origin of their multilingualism efforts and the degree of policy formalisation and implementation achieved so far.

1. Since when did your organisation start working on supporting multilingualism policies and practices and combating language bias in research assessment?

8 responses

Figure 1: Timeline of organisations' efforts to support multilingualism policies and combat language bias in research assessment (n=8)

Some institutions demonstrate long-standing engagement with multilingualism grounded in national legal or regulatory frameworks. In these contexts, multilingualism has been part of organisational operations for decades, supported by legislation that guarantees linguistic equality in communication and public administration. Such examples illustrate a mature stage of policy development, where linguistic fairness is structurally embedded rather than dependent on short-term initiatives or external mandates.

2. Does your organisation have a language policy that considers research(er) assessment?

8 responses

Figure 2: Existence of a language policy that considers research(er) assessment (n=8)

Across most responses, formal language policies explicitly linked to research assessment remain uncommon. While many institutions recognise multilingualism as a principle, implementation is typically informal or confined to specific departments. Humanities and language-related faculties, for instance, already evaluate outputs in multiple languages, yet these practices are not reflected in institutional frameworks. Some organisations offer multilingual resources for funding calls or evaluation templates, but English still dominates applications and reviews, largely to accommodate international evaluators.

This part of the questionnaire helps institutions reflect on whether their commitment to multilingualism is systematic or reliant on individual initiative. From a capacity-building perspective, it exposes the need to move from localised good practices toward coherent, institution-wide policies that ensure consistency and fairness in evaluation.

3. Is the language policy concretely integrated in the internal assessment processes of your organisation?
8 responses

Figure 3: Integration of language policy in internal assessment processes (n=8)

A smaller group of institutions report integrating multilingualism more concretely within their assessment procedures. In some cases, this is anchored in national legislation guaranteeing linguistic equality; in others, through internal guidelines or faculty-level practices that allow for non-English submissions. A few organisations have introduced mechanisms such as blind review to reduce potential language bias, though these remain limited in scale.

At the same time, reliance on English remains pervasive, particularly in international review settings, where practical considerations often outweigh inclusion goals. This tension between inclusivity and feasibility highlights an ongoing challenge: ensuring evaluators have the linguistic competence and institutional guidance needed for fair assessment.

Taken together, the findings on policy and governance show how the TF3 questionnaire functions as a self-assessment framework. It enables institutions to identify whether their approach to multilingualism is proactive or reactive, legalistic or procedural, and whether policy commitments translate into practice. As a capacity-development tool, it points to the institutional mechanisms, reviewer training, internal guidance, and cross-departmental coordination, required to turn multilingual fairness into a sustainable and system-wide reality.

Practices and institutional culture

When examining institutional practices and cultures, the findings show that while multilingualism is widely recognised as a cultural and academic value, it is not yet systematically embedded in

assessment processes. This part of the questionnaire helps institutions assess how they recognise multilingual outputs, identify barriers that limit such practices, and evaluate the inclusiveness of their assessment frameworks.

4. When assessing contributions to knowledge, does your organisation recognise and value outputs irrespective of language in which they are communicated?
8 responses

Figure 4: Organisation's recognition and valuation of outputs irrespective of language (n=8)

Findings on recognition practices show that many organisations acknowledge the value of research outputs regardless of language, but implementation is often informal or limited to certain disciplines. Departments in the humanities, such as Modern Languages, already assess and reward non-English outputs, and national frameworks like the REF permit multilingual submissions. However, this recognition is not applied consistently across fields. Respondents highlight that while there are no formal restrictions on language, English and major national languages (for example, Finnish, Swedish, or Italian) still dominate, particularly in areas influenced by bibliometric evaluation. Several institutions call for clearer mechanisms to ensure equitable treatment of outputs across all languages and to reduce evaluator bias towards English publications.

As a self-assessment tool, this question allows institutions to consider whether their recognition of multilingual outputs is supported by structured procedures or remains symbolic. From a capacity-development perspective, it helps reveal where systematic frameworks and reviewer guidance are needed to make multilingual fairness a working reality.

5. Do the members of your organisation (researchers, other employees...) face challenges and difficulties in adopting multilingualism practices?
8 responses

Figure 5: Challenges and difficulties faced by organisation members in adopting multilingualism practices (n=8)

Across institutions, a number of structural and cultural barriers limit the adoption of multilingual practices. Many respondents mention the dominance of English in publishing and the influence of metric-based visibility, which discourage researchers from disseminating work in other languages.

Language barriers can also restrict participation in international collaborations, reducing the inclusiveness of research networks.

Some organisations describe the practical burden of operating in several languages, noting that translation requirements and bilingual or trilingual obligations can be resource-intensive. Committees that include public or patient representatives encounter additional challenges when meetings are conducted entirely in English. A few institutions admit that they lack data on which researchers face these difficulties, underlining the need for systematic monitoring.

In this context, the questionnaire acts as a mirror of institutional culture, helping organisations recognise how both visible and implicit barriers affect linguistic diversity. It also serves as a diagnostic instrument, showing where investment in translation support, training, or adapted evaluation criteria could promote fairer participation.

6. In your organisation, are researchers in different disciplines and career stages involved in the development and review of the procedures, mechanisms, and processes that recognise research diversity, including from a language perspective?
8 responses

Figure 6: Involvement of researchers across disciplines and career stages in developing procedures that recognise research diversity, including language perspectives (n=8)

The responses also explore how inclusively institutions involve their communities in shaping assessment criteria. Participation in developing evaluation procedures remains limited and often confined to senior academics in formal decision-making roles. Some organisations are now broadening this process, inviting a wider range of researchers and professional staff to discuss recognition of diverse research outputs. A few examples show positive progress, including feedback mechanisms following funding calls and the inclusion of early-career researchers in evaluation panels.

However, these practices are not yet systematic, and explicit consideration of language diversity in participatory processes remains rare. The findings suggest that greater cross-disciplinary and cross-career representation is essential to build shared ownership of multilingual reform.

From a self-assessment perspective, these results help institutions gauge the inclusiveness of their governance culture, identifying whether decisions on assessment reform are collaborative or hierarchical. From a capacity-development viewpoint, they point to the need for participatory structures that embed multilingual perspectives into the co-design of assessment systems.

Taken together, these findings illustrate that while multilingualism is increasingly recognised as part of institutional culture, its implementation is uneven and context-dependent. The TF3 questionnaire helps institutions pinpoint where informal recognition should evolve into structured, equitable

practices and where greater inclusion of diverse voices can strengthen institutional capacity for sustainable multilingual reform.

Technical and infrastructural capacities

This cluster of questions explores the technical foundations that enable or limit the fair representation of multilingual research within institutional and national data systems. The responses show significant variation in infrastructural maturity, interoperability, and awareness of how information systems record and evaluate multilingual outputs.

7. Does your organisation support the use of publication databases (e.g. OpenAlex, OpenAIRE, local CRIS or Repository) which take into consideration local languages?
8 responses

Figure 7: Organisation's support for publication databases that consider local languages (n=8)

Institutions report differing levels of readiness in implementing inclusive and interoperable research information systems. Several organisations actively apply FAIR principles and align with national policies on open access to ensure that publications are registered and accessible regardless of language. Some universities operate repositories that are integrated into national CRIS infrastructures and OpenAIRE, allowing outputs in multiple languages. Others rely on platforms such as Pure, but acknowledge that these systems are not specifically configured to highlight or track multilingual publications.

In many cases, awareness of database functionality and multilingual potential varies between departments. Even where inclusive infrastructures exist, their capacity to support equitable representation is not always fully utilised. Most institutions accept publications in all languages through their repositories, yet few have procedures that guarantee equal visibility for outputs in local or minority languages.

As a self-assessment tool, this part of the questionnaire helps organisations determine whether their infrastructure simply stores multilingual outputs or actively supports their discoverability and fair evaluation. From a capacity-development perspective, it highlights where improvements are needed in metadata practices, training, and technical interoperability to make multilingualism functional at scale.

8. Does your organisation make sure that when metrics-based systems are used for different types of evaluation, publications in all languages are adequately taken into account?
8 responses

Figure 8: Consideration of publications in all languages when using metrics-based evaluation systems (n=8)

Findings on evaluation systems reveal a gradual shift toward metric-free or qualitative assessment, although integration of multilingualism into these approaches remains inconsistent. Some organisations explicitly avoid metric-based methods, following principles such as DORA and prioritising expert review over quantitative indicators. Others use national classification systems, such as publication forums, which formally recognise outputs in all languages.

At the same time, institutions acknowledge uncertainty about how evaluators apply these principles in practice. Even when formal frameworks exclude citation-based indicators, reviewers may still rely on English-language visibility as a proxy for quality. A few respondents mention that their internal systems consider elements such as international co-authorship or translated publications, which indirectly promote multilingual recognition.

However, many still lack concrete mechanisms to ensure that non-English outputs are equally valued in evaluation. While repositories may accept multilingual publications, there is little evidence that database configurations or assessment procedures provide structured accommodation for them.

Overall, the findings confirm that the questionnaire’s technical cluster functions as both a diagnostic and benchmarking tool. It enables institutions to evaluate the inclusiveness of their digital infrastructures and assess how far they align with FAIR and Open Science principles. While infrastructural awareness is growing, most organisations still need to strengthen interoperability, metadata standards, and evaluator guidance to achieve genuine multilingual equity in research assessment.

Evaluation and assessment practices

This cluster of questions explores how institutions operationalise fairness and inclusivity in research assessment. It examines whether evaluation practices follow DORA-aligned principles, how far English-language dominance is challenged, to what extent evaluator linguistic competence is considered, and whether attention to language fairness is integrated early in the planning of evaluation or funding procedures.

9. Does your organisation (as per the recommendations by DORA), during expert-based evaluation, value high quality research regardless of the publishing language or publication channel?
8 responses

Figure 9: Organisation's adherence to DORA recommendations for valuing high-quality research regardless of publishing language or channel (n=8)

Many institutions report alignment with DORA principles, prioritising the quality and relevance of research over journal prestige or language of publication. Several note that their evaluation processes already accept outputs in multiple languages, and that national frameworks such as the REF recognise multilingual submissions. These findings suggest that at a policy level, the foundation for inclusive evaluation exists, but practical implementation remains uneven.

As a self-assessment exercise, this part of the questionnaire allows institutions to determine whether their commitment to DORA and responsible metrics extends to multilingual inclusivity. From a capacity-building perspective, it underscores that evaluation mechanisms can support linguistic diversity only when multilingual submissions are actively encouraged, transparently reviewed, and valued on equal terms.

10. Does your organisation adhere to the principle that writing in English does not confer a merit per se superior to publications in other languages?
8 responses

Figure 10: Organisation's adherence to the principle that writing in English does not confer superior merit (n=8)

A majority of the respondents acknowledge the importance of treating all publication languages equally, though only a few have formalised this stance in institutional policy. Some organisations promote national-language communication and outreach, particularly within the humanities and social sciences, while others reject English-language dominance in principle but lack explicit criteria to reinforce this in practice.

The questionnaire helps institutions gauge how deeply their stated values are embedded within assessment frameworks. It differentiates between rhetorical support for multilingualism and concrete operational mechanisms that uphold it. From a capacity-development angle, these results highlight the need for formal guidelines, communication strategies, and evaluative criteria that move language equity beyond aspiration toward institutional routine.

13. When choosing evaluators, does your organisation ensure that they have required language skills to assess research outputs in relevant languages?

8 responses

Figure 11: Organisation's consideration of evaluator language skills for assessing research outputs in relevant languages (n=8)

Responses regarding evaluator competence reveal that English remains the predominant language of assessment, especially in international review contexts. Some organisations assess evaluator language skills indirectly, through professional background or country of work, while others omit this consideration entirely. In language-related fields, evaluators are expected to review work in both English and the relevant research language, but this remains an exception.

Institutions identify this as a clear policy gap and indicate plans to address it through future reforms. Cases where reviewers lack proficiency in the research language highlight the risk of bias even in well-intentioned systems. As a self-assessment tool, the questionnaire helps organisations reflect on whether evaluator selection procedures align with their multilingual goals. As a capacity-evaluation measure, it points to the need for structured reviewer training, language competence mapping, and procedural safeguards to ensure fair assessment across languages.

15. Does your organisation take language and potential language biases into consideration already when planning evaluation, assessment or funding procedures?

8 responses

Figure 12: Organisation's consideration of language and potential language biases in planning evaluation, assessment, or funding procedures (n=8)

Few institutions currently formalise language considerations during the planning stage of evaluation or funding. Some report growing informal awareness, allowing flexibility in English proficiency or recognising other main publication languages in specific disciplines. Others mention initial steps to include multilingual aspects in comparative or international research assessments.

A handful of organisations value the dissemination or translation of research outputs as part of their evaluation criteria, indirectly supporting language fairness. Still, most lack formalised procedures, and some even anticipate that future reliance on AI translation tools could address language barriers—a sign that policy in this area remains underdeveloped.

Overall, these findings demonstrate that multilingualism is increasingly recognised as a component of fair assessment but remains inconsistently implemented. The TF3 questionnaire offers institutions both a diagnostic and developmental framework, encouraging them to examine evaluator competence, procedural design, and early policy planning. Strengthening these elements is essential for achieving sustainable fairness across linguistic contexts.

Values and equity of multilingualism

The findings in this cluster show how institutions interpret multilingualism not only as a procedural concern but also as a matter of academic values, cultural equity, and societal relevance. Across responses, recognition of linguistic diversity as a cultural and social good is widespread, yet its translation into formal research assessment frameworks remains limited and uneven.

11. Does your organisation recognise that multilingualism favours the development of socially relevant research and contributes to sustaining cultural diversity?
8 responses

Figure 13: Organisation's recognition that multilingualism favours socially relevant research and contributes to sustaining cultural diversity (n=8)

Many institutions affirm that multilingualism forms part of their organisational ethos or national legal context, even when it is not directly linked to assessment practices. In some countries, legislation explicitly protects linguistic diversity as a component of the higher education system, ensuring that national languages remain visible in research communication. Centres and programmes devoted to literacy and multilingualism similarly embed inclusivity and cultural diversity in their missions.

At the same time, most respondents note that explicit institutional policies connecting multilingualism to evaluation are still absent. Support for language diversity tends to rest on shared institutional values rather than formal governance structures. This points to the need for mechanisms that connect cultural principles with concrete assessment practices.

As a self-assessment dimension, this part of the questionnaire helps institutions distinguish between symbolic support for multilingualism and tangible policy implementation. From a capacity-development perspective, it highlights where value-based commitments could be formalised through guidelines or evaluation criteria that reward multilingual scholarship.

12. Does your organisation consider excellence in local research as relevant and value the use of local, regional and national languages as high-quality...ence, helping make such research available to all?
8 responses

Figure 14: Organisation's consideration of excellence in local research and value of local, regional, and national languages (n=8).

Institutions also reflect on whether research in local or national languages is recognised as part of academic excellence. Some national systems already incorporate this through publication classifications that include local-language venues, particularly in the humanities and social sciences. These frameworks demonstrate that local engagement and cultural specificity can coexist with research excellence, challenging the assumption that only international or English-language outputs convey quality.

Respondents from humanities-focused institutions note that national-language publications remain essential for preserving cultural identity and ensuring accessibility to broader audiences. Yet, English continues to dominate in fields shaped by international collaboration or metrics-based evaluation, limiting the perceived value of local-language work.

Through this question, institutions can assess whether their evaluation systems reflect the full diversity of scholarly communication within their national and disciplinary contexts. As a capacity indicator, it identifies opportunities to broaden institutional and national frameworks so that multilingual dissemination becomes a visible and rewarded aspect of responsible research assessment.

Viewed collectively, these findings show that while the cultural and social significance of multilingualism is widely acknowledged, its integration into research assessment remains partial. The TF3 questionnaire thus encourages institutions to translate values into action, bridging the gap between cultural recognition and operational reform in support of a more equitable multilingual research ecosystem.

Alignment with Broader Reform Movements

The responses to this final question show that many institutions position their multilingualism initiatives within the broader landscape of global research assessment reform. Several organisations have formally endorsed the Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA), while others participate in complementary frameworks such as the Leiden Manifesto, the Barcelona Declaration on Open Research Information, and the CoARA Agreement.

14. Did your organisation endorse, beyond CoARA, also Helsinki, DORA or any other international declarations or initiatives?
8 responses

Figure 15: Organisation’s endorsement of international declarations beyond CoARA, including Helsinki, DORA, and others (n=8)

For some institutions, engagement with these initiatives reflects a mature, values-based commitment to transparency, inclusivity, and openness in research assessment. Endorsement of DORA or similar declarations is seen not merely as a policy statement but as part of a wider cultural transformation towards responsible evaluation. Other organisations are still in the exploratory phase, assessing which international frameworks align best with their strategic priorities and integrating such reflection into ongoing action plan development.

Viewed through a self-assessment lens, this aspect of the questionnaire enables institutions to gauge their position within the international reform ecosystem and to identify gaps in coherence across multiple frameworks. From a capacity-development perspective, it provides insight into institutional readiness for collaboration, collective learning, and policy harmonisation, reinforcing the link between multilingual fairness and the broader objectives of Open Science.

Looking across these findings, it becomes evident that while many organisations share the values of equity, inclusivity, and openness, their translation into concrete institutional frameworks remains incomplete. The TF3 questionnaire offers a structured means of connecting local and institutional progress on multilingualism with global reform efforts, helping organisations move from value affirmation to practical implementation within a shared vision of fair and responsible research assessment.

5. Recommendations for the future use of the TF3 questionnaire

The TF3 questionnaire should be seen as both a diagnostic and developmental instrument for assessing institutional readiness in addressing multilingualism in research assessment. Based on the analysis of responses, this chapter offers recommendations for how the tool could be refined and applied by other institutions in future phases of CoARA implementation and beyond.

R1 – Use the questionnaire as a structured self-assessment framework

Institutions should employ the questionnaire as a structured reflection tool to map the maturity of their policies and practices on multilingualism. The 16-question structure covers complementary dimensions, policy, governance, culture, infrastructure, evaluation, and values, enabling organisations to position themselves along a continuum from early awareness to systemic implementation. Conducting the self-assessment periodically, for example every two years, would allow institutions to monitor progress, document improvements, and demonstrate alignment with CoARA commitments.

Implementation tip: Establish an internal working group, including representatives from governance, research administration, libraries, and academic departments, to complete the questionnaire collectively. This collaborative approach promotes internal dialogue and strengthens cross-departmental ownership of multilingual reform.

R2 – Employ the questionnaire as a capacity-building and benchmarking tool

Beyond self-assessment, the questionnaire can function as a capacity-evaluation instrument, revealing where institutional infrastructure or expertise requires strengthening. By analysing the responses in aggregate, institutions can benchmark their progress against similar organisations, identifying shared challenges such as the dominance of English in evaluation or the lack of multilingual data infrastructure.

Implementation tip: Results could be aggregated across institutional networks (for example, by national research councils or consortia) to identify common needs and inform joint capacity-building programmes, including training for evaluators or technical staff on multilingual metadata and FAIR practices.

R3 – Link the questionnaire to policy and action planning

The questionnaire should serve not only as a reflective tool but also as a policy-development instrument. Each cluster of questions can be linked to corresponding policy objectives—such as developing language policies, adapting repositories, or formalising evaluator guidelines. The results can feed directly into institutional action plans or national roadmaps on multilingualism and open science.

Implementation tip: After completing the questionnaire, institutions could produce a short “Multilingualism in Research Assessment Action Plan,” summarising the main findings, identified gaps, and short-, medium-, and long-term objectives for policy improvement.

R4 – Embed the questionnaire into broader research assessment reform initiatives

Given its alignment with CoARA, DORA, and the Helsinki Initiative, the questionnaire should be embedded into ongoing research assessment reform frameworks. Using the instrument in conjunction with other policy evaluation tools will promote coherence and reinforce multilingualism as a key dimension of responsible research evaluation.

Implementation tip: Institutions participating in CoARA reform working groups or DORA-aligned initiatives could integrate the questionnaire into their regular reporting cycles, using it to evidence progress on inclusivity and equity.

R5 – Ensure data reusability and comparative learning

To maximise the collective value of the questionnaire, institutions should adopt common data-sharing and documentation practices. Anonymised results could be stored in open repositories or visualised through dashboards, supporting cross-institutional learning and transparency in multilingual policy development.

Implementation tip: TF3 developed an openly licensed version of the questionnaire. This would enable other CoARA task forces, national consortia, or research networks to adapt the tool to their local contexts.

Organisations affiliated to this WG

- Federation of Finnish Learned Societies (TSV), Finland
- Marie Curie Alumni Association (MCAA), Global
- OPERAS AISBL, Europe
- Coimbra Group, Europe
- European Civil Society Platform for Multilingualism, Europe
- Adam Mickiewicz University (AMU), Poland
- ANR – French National Research Agency, France
- CNRS, France
- cOAlition S, Europe
- Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), Spain
- Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR), Italy
- Eurodoc, Europe
- European Alliance for SSH (EASSH), Europe
- European Network for Research Evaluation in the Social Sciences and the Humanities (ENRESSH), Europe
- EuroScience – the European Association for the Advancement of Science and Technology, Europe
- Fonds de recherche du Québec (observer)
- Global Young Academy (GYA)
- Hanken School of Economics (Hanken), Finland
- Initiative for Science in Europe (ISE), Europe
- Italian national agency for the evaluation of universities and research institutes (ANVUR), Italy
- Latin American Forum on Research Assessment (CLACSO-FOLEC), Argentina
- Lusófona University, Portugal
- NIFU – Nordic institute for studies in innovation, research and education, Norway
- Research Council of Finland, Finland
- Research Foundation Flanders (FWO), Belgium
- Sorbonne Université, France
- Stockholm University, Sweden
- Tampere University (TAU), Finland

- TOUR4EU Tuscan Organisation of Universities in Europe (TOUR4EU), Italy
- translatE network on language barriers in environmental sciences, University of Queensland, Australia
- UNESCO Chair on Open Science, University of Montréal, Canada
- Università degli Studi di Milano (UMI), Italy
- Università di Milano-Bicocca (UNIMIB), Italy
- Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, Spain
- Universities Norway (UHR), Norway
- University of Antwerp, (UAntwerp), Belgium
- University of Jyväskylä, Finland
- University of Leiden (LEI), Netherlands
- University of Lleida
- University of Turku (UTU), Finland
- University of Warwick
- University Paris Nanterre, France

CoARA

The Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) is a collective of organisations committed to reforming the methods and processes by which research, researchers, and research organisations are evaluated. Current research assessment methods rely heavily on publication-based metrics such as citation counts, and often fail to recognise the wide array of contributions made by researchers.

Over 700 research organisations, funders, assessment authorities, professional societies, and their associations have agreed on a common direction and guiding principles to implement reform in the assessment of research, researchers, and research organisations, outlined in the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#) published in July 2022 which provides an outline for reform and implementation.

Find out more about CoARA at www.coara.eu.

Working Group Overview

Working Groups are key communities of practice that work to implement research assessment reform in specific thematic areas. Participating members exchange knowledge, learn from each other's experience, discuss and develop outputs to advance research assessment and support the implementation of members' commitments.

The mission of the WG Multilingualism and Language Biases in Research Assessment is to foster an academic culture that values diverse competencies, interactions, and communications in all languages without exclusions or priorities. The main objectives of the Working Group are to:

1. Raise awareness across all fields about the importance of “multilingualism in practice of science, in scientific publications and in academic communications” (UNESCO);
2. Provide institutions with guidelines, toolbox and implementation proposal for recognizing, rewarding and incentivizing research carried out and communicated in all languages, and for addressing language biases in metrics, expert-assessment and rankings.